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The structural and electrophysiological properties of progesterone receptor expressing neurons vary along the anterior-posterior axis of the ventromedial hypothalamus and undergo local changes across the reproductive cycle

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1 **Title:** The structural and electrophysiological properties of progesterone receptor
2 expressing neurons vary along the anterior-posterior axis of the ventromedial
3 hypothalamus and undergo local changes across the reproductive cycle

4

5 **Abbreviated title:** Local hypothalamic changes across the reproductive cycle

6

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23 The authors declare no competing interests.

1

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45 **Abstract**

46 Sex hormone levels continuously fluctuate across the reproductive cycle, changing the
47 activity of neuronal circuits to coordinate female behavior and reproductive capacity.
48 The ventrolateral division of the ventromedial hypothalamus (VMHvl) contains neurons
49 expressing receptors for sex hormones and its function is intimately linked to female
50 sexual receptivity. However, recent findings suggest that the VMHvl is functionally
51 heterogeneous. Here, we used whole recordings and intracellular labeling to
52 characterize the electrophysiological and morphological properties of individual VMHvl
53 neurons in naturally cycling females and report the existence of multiple
54 electrophysiological phenotypes within the VMHvl. We found that the properties of
55 progesterone receptor expressing (PR+) neurons, but not PR- neurons, depended
56 systematically on the neuron's location along the anterior-posterior axis of the VMHvl
57 and the phase within the reproductive cycle. Prominent amongst this, the resting
58 membrane potential of anterior PR+ neurons decreased during the receptive phase,
59 while the excitability of medial PR+ neurons increased during the non-receptive phase.
60 During the receptive phase of the cycle, posterior PR+ neurons simultaneously showed
61 an increase in dendritic complexity and a decrease in spine density. These findings
62 reveal an extensive diversity of local rules driving structural and physiological changes
63 in response to fluctuating levels of sex hormones, supporting the anatomical and
64 functional subdivision of the VMHvl and its possible role in the orchestration of different
65 aspects of female socio-sexual behavior.

66

67 **Significance Statement**

68 Fluctuating levels of sex hormones coordinate female behavior with their reproductive
69 capacity by acting on neurons expressing their specific receptors. However, it is poorly
70 understood how this seemingly simple message is integrated in local circuits to
71 coordinate complex behavioral responses. Here we show evidence that progesterone
72 receptor expressing neurons of the VMHvl undergo local and specific changes in
73 structure and physiology, suggesting a compartmentalized action of the fluctuating
74 systemic levels of sex hormone across the reproductive cycle, depending on their
75 location in this hypothalamic nucleus.

76

77 **Keywords:** Ventrolateral part of the ventromedial hypothalamus; Progesterone
78 receptor; Structural plasticity; Whole cell recordings; Intrinsic excitability; Reproductive
79 cycle.

80

81 **Introduction**

82 Female reproductive physiology and behavior are under the control of the ovarian sex
83 hormones estrogen and progesterone, whose fluctuating levels act reversibly in the
84 female brain, organizing the activity of neural circuits to synchronize sexual behavior
85 with reproductive capacity (Jennings & de Lecea, 2020; Snoeren, 2018). The
86 ventrolateral division of the ventromedial hypothalamus (VMHvl) is crucial for female
87 reproductive behavior, in particular for the display of lordosis, the female acceptance
88 posture. Non-specific electrolytic lesions (Pfaff & Sakuma, 1979a) or ablation of
89 genetically delineated neuronal populations (Rissman et al., 1997; Yang et al., 2013) of
90 the VMHvl virtually abolish lordosis, while electrical stimulation at the same location
91 enhances the probability of females displaying it (Pfaff & Sakuma, 1979b). Importantly,
92 VMHvl neurons have rich expression of receptors for estrogen (ER) and progesterone
93 (PR) and therefore are sensitive to the fluctuating levels of these sex hormones across
94 the reproductive cycle (Jennings & de Lecea, 2020; Snoeren, 2018). In accordance,
95 local infusion of sex hormones in the VMHvl increases female receptivity (Rubin &
96 Barfield, 1983a) while male-evoked activity in this hypothalamic nucleus is enhanced
97 when females are sexually receptive (Nomoto & Lima, 2015). Moreover, the output of
98 PR-expressing neurons of the VMHvl is altered across the reproductive cycle and this
99 cyclic remodeling is fundamental for the expression of acceptance when females are
100 sexual receptive (Inoue et al., 2019). In summary, vast evidence highlights the
101 importance of the VMHvl for coordinating female's reproductive state with sexual
102 receptivity.

103

104 Several studies have shown a large diversity of neuronal types with a wide variety of
105 cellular identities within the VMHvl (Flanagan-Cato, 2011; Kim et al., 2019; McClellan et
106 al., 2006). In addition, the generation of Cre lines providing access to ER- and PR-
107 expressing neurons uncovered further anatomical and functional subdivisions across
108 the nucleus' anterior-posterior axis (AP axis) (Flanagan-Cato, 2011; Hashikawa et al.,
109 2017; Inoue et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2019; Lo et al., 2019; McClellan et al., 2006; Wang
110 et al., 2019), revealing a much broader role of this hypothalamic region in the control of
111 different aspects of female socio-sexual behavior. While regulation of female sexual
112 receptivity seems to be localized to the most posterior-lateral part of the VMHvl, its
113 posterior-medial division is involved in aggressive behavior towards intruders in mothers
114 (Hashikawa et al., 2017). Moreover, it was recently shown that ER-expressing neurons
115 in the anterior portion of the VMHvl are important for self-defense in males (Wang et al.,
116 2019). The connectivity of ER-expressing neurons also varies across the AP axis,
117 further supporting the idea of topographic heterogeneity within this small nucleus (Lo et
118 al., 2019).

119 How fluctuating levels of sex hormones affect the properties and function of VMHvl
120 neurons remains poorly understood. Most studies aimed at elucidating the impact of sex
121 hormones on neuronal activity in this region have focused on the structural properties of
122 VMHvl neurons. The majority of neurons in the VMHvl have a long primary dendrite
123 (LPD) that extends outside the nucleus, receiving inputs from other forebrain regions, a
124 short primary (SPD), and secondary dendrites that may integrate local inputs (Calizo &
125 Flanagan-cato, 2000; Millhouse, 1973). Previous studies in rodents have shown that
126 externally primed estradiol treatment shortens LPDs and reduces dendritic density in

127 the VMHvl, effects which are reversed by progesterone (Griffin et al., 2010; Griffin &
128 Flanagan-Cato, 2008). In addition, externally applied ovarian hormones increase the
129 density of dendritic spines on the SPD of VMHvl neurons (Calizo & Flanagan-cato,
130 2000), and decrease the spine density on the LPD of VMHvl neurons (Calizo &
131 Flanagan-cato, 2002). Moreover, treatment with estrogen was found to lead to an
132 increase in the size of neuronal somata in the VMHvl (Carrer & Aoki, 1982; Griffin &
133 Flanagan-cato, 2011). More recently, it was shown that elevation in the concentration of
134 circulating estrogen increases the number of axon terminals of PR-expressing VMHvl
135 neurons that project to the anteroventral periventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus in
136 female mice and that this plasticity is necessary for sexual receptivity (Inoue et al.,
137 2019). Interestingly, aggressive behavior in males correlates with androgen levels in
138 circulation and is dependent on the physiological and structural plasticity of ER-
139 expressing neurons in the VMHvl (Stagkourakis et al., 2020). However, the
140 electrophysiological properties of VMHvl neurons across the reproductive cycle have
141 received very little attention (but see Kow and Pfaff, 1985 and Booth and Wyman,
142 2010).

143 A noteworthy common factor among the vast majority of previous studies on the effects
144 of sex hormones on VMHvl neurons and behavior is that they have been performed in
145 ovariectomized females in which sex hormones were systemically administered at
146 concentrations that do not always match the physiological levels that are observed in
147 naturally cycling females (Liu & Shi, 2015). Moreover, despite the growing evidence
148 suggesting anatomical and functional diversity of the VMHvl, most studies have been
149 largely focused on its most posterior levels (Hashikawa et al., 2017; Inoue et al., 2019;

150 Yang et al., 2013). However, the VMHvl extends slightly more than a millimeter across
151 the base of the hypothalamus (Kim et al., 2019; Lo et al., 2019), and sex hormone
152 receptor expressing neurons are homogeneously distributed throughout (Kim et al.,
153 2019; Sá & Fonseca, 2017). If and how the structural and physiological properties of
154 VMHvl neurons along its AP axis vary across the female reproductive cycle remains
155 elusive.

156 In order to gain a more complete understanding of the function of the VMHvl, in the
157 present study we investigated the structural and electrophysiological properties of
158 genetically delineated neurons along the VMHvl AP axis and across the reproductive
159 cycle of naturally cycling females. We focused our efforts on neurons expressing the
160 progesterone receptor, as they are fundamental for female sexual behavior (Yang et al.,
161 2013). To do so, we obtained slices from receptive and non-receptive females and
162 performed in vitro whole-cell recordings of PR expressing (PR+) and PR non-expressing
163 (PR-) neurons, with subsequent reconstruction of the recorded neurons to characterize
164 their electrophysiological and structural properties.

165 Here we report the existence of multiple electrophysiological phenotypes within the
166 VMHvl and a wide variety of structural and physiological properties across the AP axis
167 of the VMHvl, which are specific for PR+ neurons and that vary locally across the
168 reproductive cycle. For instance, the membrane resting potential of anterior PR+
169 neurons decreases during the receptive phase, while the excitability of medial PR+
170 increases when females are non-receptive. During the receptive phase of the cycle,
171 posterior PR+ neurons simultaneously undergo an increase in dendritic complexity and
172 a decrease in spine density. These findings reveal an extensive diversity of local rules

173 driving structural and physiological changes in response to fluctuating levels of sex
174 hormones, supporting the anatomical and functional subdivision of the VMHvl and its
175 possible role in the orchestration of different aspects of female socio-sexual behavior.

176 **Materials and Methods**

177 **Animals**

178 Data was collected from adult PR-Cre-R26R-EYFP (for short PR-EYFP) female mice (2-
179 9 months). PR-EYFP mice express the Enhanced Yellow Fluorescent Protein (EYFP) in
180 cells expressing progesterone receptor (PR+) using the Cre-lox recombination system.
181 Briefly, these mice result from the cross-breeding of B6129S(Cg)-
182 Pgrtm1.1(Cre)Shah/AndJ75 mice (for short PRCre; JAX stock #017915; Yang et al.,
183 2013), containing the Cre recombinase, which is expressed simultaneously with
184 endogenous PR gene, with B6.129X1-Gt(ROSA26Sortm1(EYFP)Cos/J177 mice (for
185 short R26R-EYFP; JAX stock #006148; Srinivas et al., 2001) that have the EYFP gene
186 following a STOP sequence flanked by loxP. Therefore, in their offspring, heterozygous
187 for both PR-Cre and R26R-EYFP alleles, loxP cassettes are removed by the action of
188 Cre recombinase specifically in cells expressing PR, resulting in EYFP expression.

189 For the visualization of GABAergic somas, we used double heterozygous mice that
190 resulted from the cross-breeding of B6J.129S6(FVB)-Slc32a1^{tm2(cre)Lowl}/MwarJ (for short
191 Vgat-ires-Cre knock-in; JAX stock #028862; Vong et al., 2011) with B6;129S6-
192 Gt(ROSA)26Sor^{tm9(CAG-tdTomato)Hze}/J (for short Ai9; JAX stock #007905; Madisen et al.,
193 2010). Using the previously described Cre dependent recombinase method, these mice

194 express the fluorescent marker tdTomato under the promoter of the vesicular
195 transporter of GABA.

196 Animals were kept under controlled temperature of 23 ± 1 °C and photoperiod of
197 reversed 12 h light/dark cycle (light available from 8p.m. to 8a.m.) conditions and group-
198 housed in standard cages with environmental enrichment elements. Food and water
199 were provided *ad libitum*. Females were weaned at 20-21 days of age and group-
200 housed with two to five animals.

201 After reaching 6 weeks of age, females were exposed to adult C57BL/6 male soiled
202 bedding once per week to stimulate the natural reproductive cycle. All procedures were
203 carried out in accordance with the animal protocols approved by the Portuguese
204 National Authority for Animal Health (*Direcção Geral de Alimentação e Veterinária*;
205 DGAV) and the Commission for Experimentation and Animal Welfare of the
206 Champalimaud Centre for the Unknown (*Órgão para o Bem Estar Animal*; ORBEA).

207

208 **Reproductive Cycle Monitoring**

209 To assess the reproductive state of naturally cycling female mice, vaginal cytology
210 samples were collected every morning for at least one entire cycle (four/five consecutive
211 days). This collection was done by vaginal lavage using a pipette (T-210-Y, AXYGEN,
212 with its tip cut): 10 μ L of 0.01M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) was gently flushed into
213 the vagina and back out three or four times without touching the vaginal wall to avoid
214 cervical stimulation and pseudopregnancy. The flush containing vaginal fluid was
215 transferred to a glass slide and dried (Caligioni, 2009). Papanicolaou staining was used

216 to differentiate cells (Bio-Optica protocol) and they were observed under a Zeiss
217 AxioScope A1 brightfield microscope with a 10x objective. The identification of the
218 reproductive cycle phase was done based on the proportion of each cell type in the
219 smear. Proestrus is characterized by nucleated epithelial cells. In estrus the main cells
220 present in the vaginal secretion are cornified squamous epithelial cells, clustered with
221 irregular shape. These start to be replaced by leukocytes during metestrus, being these
222 predominant cells in diestrus (Caligioni, 2009; Pfau, 1999; Snoeren, 2018).
223 Experiments were performed when females were in proestrus/estrus (sexually
224 receptive) or in diestrus (sexually non-receptive).

225 ***Ex vivo* Electrophysiological Recordings**

226 PR-Cre-EYFP mice were deeply anesthetized with isoflurane and decapitated 1-2 hours
227 after the phase of the cycle identification by pap smearing. This protocol is used by the
228 laboratory for behavioral experiments (Nomoto & Lima, 2015). After decapitation, brains
229 were quickly removed and placed into “ice cold” slicing solution containing (in mM): 0.66
230 kynurenic acid, 3.63 pyruvate, 2.5 KCl, 1.25 NaH₂PO₄, 26 NaHCO₃, 10 D-Glucose,
231 230 Sucrose, 0.5 CaCl₂, 10 MgSO₄, and bubbled with 5% CO₂ and 95% O₂. Coronal
232 sections with 300µm containing the VMH were cut using a vibratome (Leica VT1200) in
233 the same “ice cold” slicing solution. Slices were recovered in oxygenated artificial
234 cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF) containing (in mM): 127 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 25 NaHCO₃, 1.25
235 NaH₂PO₄, 25 D-Glucose, 2 CaCl₂, and 1 MgCl₂, at 34°C for 30 minutes and stored in
236 the same solution at room temperature before being transferred to the recording
237 chamber.

238 Whole-cell recordings were made under a SliceScope Pro (Scientifica) microscope with
239 the slices submerged in ACSF. A beam of blue light generated with a LED illumination
240 system (CoolLED, pE300) was passed through an immersion objective (Olympus, 40x)
241 to achieve wide field illumination of the slice. PR+ neurons were identified by their
242 natural fluorescence under the microscope and PR- by the absence of fluorescence. A
243 standard GFP filter cube (Thorlabs) was used to filter EYFP emission. EYFP
244 expression, and therefore fluorescence levels, are independent of the reproductive
245 cycle, as after Cre recombination, the expression of the fluorescent protein is dependent
246 on the rosa locus. Patch recording pipettes (resistance 3-5M Ω) were filled with internal
247 solution containing (in mM): 135 K-Gluconate, 10 HEPES, 10 Na-phosphocreatine, 3
248 Na-L-ascorbate, 4 MgCl₂, 4 Na-ATP, 0.4 Na-GTP (pH 7.2 adjusted with NaOH and
249 osmolarity ~292mOs) and 0.1% of biocytin. Internal solution was filtered with a 0.2 μ m
250 pore size cellulose acetate filter tip. A Multiclamp 700B amplifier and digitized at 10KHz
251 with a Digidata 1440a digitizer (both from Molecular Devices) were used and the data
252 was filtered online with a 10KHz low-pass filter.

253 We applied a test-pulse of -10mV for 100ms in voltage-clamp mode at -70mV to monitor
254 membrane capacitance and series resistance. To determine excitability and firing
255 properties, current-clamp experiments were performed at resting potential by applying
256 series of 1000ms current pulses between 0 and 240pA with an increasing interval of
257 30pA at a frequency of 0.1Hz. Hyperpolarization-activated inward current (I_h current)
258 and rebound firing were measured with a 1000ms current pulse at -90pA. The bridge
259 balance was semi-automatically compensated using Axon pCLAMP 10 (Molecular
260 Devices).

261 After recording, the pipette was carefully withdrawn from the neurons to allow the
262 resealing of the membrane and the diffusion of biocytin inside the neuron. Slices were
263 then transferred to a multi-well plate containing 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) for ~1 hour
264 for fixation and then transferred to 0.01M PBS for storage prior to immunostaining.

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266

267

268 **Histology**

269 To visualize biocytin filling, slices were incubated in streptavidin-Alexa Fluor 488
270 Conjugate (Invitrogen; concentration: 1:200) with 0.3% Triton X-100 in 0.01M PBS at
271 room temperature for 3 hours in dark. After washing three times with 0.01M PBS for 30
272 minutes each, sections were mounted in glass slides (Menzel-Glazer), coverslipped
273 (Marienfeld) with Mowiol mounting medium (Sigma-Aldrich) and the edges sealed with
274 clear nail polish. For tissue collection, VGat-Cre-tdtomato mice were deeply
275 anesthetized with a lethal amount of a mixture of 12% of ketamine (Imalgene 1000,
276 Merial) and 8% of xylazine (Rompun 2%, Bayer) in saline solution and perfused
277 transcardially with 0.01M PBS followed by 4% PFA in PBS. The brains were removed,
278 fixated in the 4% PFA solution for ~1 hour and transferred to a 30% sucrose (Sigma-
279 Aldrich) in 0.01M Phosphate-Buffer and 0.1% Sodium Azide (ACROS Organics) to allow
280 cryopreservation. Brains were then frozen and coronal sections with 45 μ m thickness
281 were obtained from the VMH using a freezing sliding microtome (SM2000R, Leica).
282 Histological sections and fixed ex vivo brain slices were imaged with a Zeiss LSM 710
283 confocal laser scanning microscope with a 10x and a 25x magnification objectives.

284

285 **Electrophysiological Data Analysis**

286 A total of 144 recorded neurons were used in the present study. Please see Table 1 and
287 Figure 1 for the numbers of recorded PR+ and PR- neurons, across the reproductive
288 cycle and AP axis.

289 The action potentials recorded in current-clamp mode were analyzed with custom-
290 written MATLAB code. Each spike within the spike trains obtained upon current injection
291 were detected and used to determine the firing frequency, interspike interval (ISI),
292 threshold to spike, latency to spike and coefficient of variation calculated at a fixed
293 current injection of 150pA). The coefficient of variation was calculated using the
294 following formula (Holt et al., 1996):

$$CV2 = \frac{2|ISI_{n+1} - ISI_n|}{(ISI_{n+1} + ISI_n)}$$

295 The rebound action potentials observed after injecting hyperpolarizing currents were
296 obtained using the same method.

297 The first action potential obtained of each spiking sweep was used to calculate the spike
298 amplitude and spike half-width to prevent frequency dependent artifacts in the spike
299 shape caused by sodium and potassium channel inactivation.

300 The resting potential was determined by averaging the membrane voltage values before
301 the current injection and the Ih current amplitude was calculated by the difference
302 between the early and late phase of a hyperpolarizing current pulse.

303 Voltage clamp test-pulses were analyzed using Clampfit 10.7 Software (Molecular
304 Devices, LLC) and access resistance (Ra), membrane resistance (Rm), time constant
305 (τ) and capacitance were calculated. Only neurons with access resistance 1/10th lower

306 than the membrane resistance were used for analysis. Access resistance was
307 comparable across location, genotype and the phase of the cycle in the present study.
308 The passive membrane properties membrane resistance (R_m), membrane capacitance
309 (C_{mem}), and membrane time constant (τ) were obtained immediately after membrane
310 rupture, using a square voltage step (-10mV, 100ms). The access resistance was
311 determined by measuring the amplitude of the current response to the command
312 voltage step and the membrane resistance as the difference between the baseline and
313 the holding current in the steady state after the capacitive decay, by applying the ohm's
314 law. The membrane time constant was determined by a single exponential fit of the
315 decay phase in response to the square pulse. An approximation of the capacitance was
316 made by using the formula:

$$\tau = \text{membrane capacitance} * \text{access resistance}$$

317 The PCA-initialized t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (tSNE) on the firing
318 rates and its subsequent clustering were performed using the *tsne* and *kmeans*
319 functions of Matlab 2020a.

320

321 **Neuronal Reconstruction and Image Data Analysis**

322 A total of 180 neurons VMHvl neurons were filled with biocytin in acute slices obtained
323 from PR-EYFP female mice using whole-cell recording pipettes. These slices containing
324 biocytin filled neurons were fixed and stained with streptavidin-Alexa 488 Conjugated for
325 the subsequent reconstruction of neuronal structure. In our hands, the native EYFP
326 signal systematically bleached after slice fixation, being several fold dimmer than the
327 fluorescence obtained with Streptavidin-Alexa 488. Therefore, with our confocal

328 settings, no somatic EYFP signal was obtained despite their spectral overlap. Please
329 refer to Table 2 and Figure 6 for the numbers of filled PR+ and PR- neurons across the
330 reproductive cycle and AP axis.

331 To determine the Bregma coordinate for each reconstructed neuron and ensure that its
332 location fell within the VMHvl, in a separate experiment we first assessed the extension
333 of the VMHvl, taking advantage of the VGAT-tdTomato. The VMH is organized in a core
334 of glutamatergic neurons (Ziegler et al 2002, Yamamoto et al 2018) and a surrounding
335 shell with higher density of GABAergic neurons (Yamamoto et al 2018). Therefore, we
336 assessed the AP extension of the VMH by counting consecutive slices in which the
337 VMH was detectable, as shown by a decrease of the VGAT-tdTomato signal (Fig. 6A)
338 and multiplying by the thickness of the histological slices. A sharp transition from low to
339 high tdTomato fluorescence was observed both in its anterior limit (near the anterior
340 hypothalamus) as well as with its posterior limit (near the premammillary hypothalamus)
341 (data not shown). The extension obtained matched the extension illustrated by the
342 Paxinos Brain Atlas: Anterior limit= 1.05 to posterior limit= 2.06 from Bregma (that is,
343 the VMHvl spans for ~1 mm). For each mouse, we systematically sampled 3
344 consecutive levels of the VMH in slices of 300 microns of thickness. We thus
345 categorized each sampling level as anterior (Bregma -1.05 to -1.30 mm approx.), medial
346 (Bregma -1.30 to -1.65 mm approx.), and posterior (Bregma -1.65 to -2.00 mm approx.)
347 levels of the VMH (Fig. 6B-C). Localization of the reconstructed neurons in the brain
348 was assessed by matching in Adobe Illustrator CS6 (Adobe Systems Incorporated) the
349 confocal images of the neurons with adapted sections from the Paxinos brain atlas
350 (Franklin & Paxinos, 2008). Only the neurons inside the defined boundaries of the

351 VMHvl were considered for quantification. We used the Simple Neurite Tracer (Longair
352 et al., 2011) package from Fiji/ImageJ software (Schindelin et al., 2012) to analyze the
353 morphological properties and Sholl profiles of the neurons filled with biocytin. The Cell
354 Counter Fiji/ImageJ plugin was used to manually count spines.

355 Cut and resealed dendrites (identified as a globular thickening in the extreme of a
356 dendrite) were quantified for every neuron and did not reveal significant differences
357 across groups (Number of cut dendrites/total number of dendrites quantified per group
358 for PR+ neurons: 21/126 in anteriorNon-Rec, 19/120 in anteriorRec, 20/116 in
359 medialNon-Rec, 31/151 in medialRec, 26/131 in posteriorNon-Rec and 26/121 in
360 posteriorRec. And for PR- neurons: 26/130 in anteriorNon-Rec, 16/70 in anteriorRec,
361 19/95 in medialNon-Rec, 15/85 in medialRec, 26/100 in posteriorNon-Rec and 17/100 in
362 posteriorRec). When tested with a Fisher's exact test, neither PR+ nor PR- revealed
363 statistical difference in the proportion of cut dendrites. We thus assume that this
364 unavoidable artifact of our method of neuronal recording and reconstruction did not add
365 any group-specific bias in the structural quantification.

366 In our hands, as well as in previous studies (Calizo & Flanagan-cato, 2000), the
367 intracellular labeling of VMHvl neurons did not always make their thin axonal process
368 visible, and therefore, the axons identified were not considered for analysis.

369 Graphs were made using custom made MATLAB code or GraphPad Prism 8 Software.

370

371 **Statistical Analyses**

372 Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 8 Software. Normality of the
373 residuals was tested with the D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus K2 test. When normally

374 distributed, three-way ANOVA tests were performed to compare groups in different
375 phases of the cycle (D vs PE) vs location in the AP axis (anterior vs medial vs posterior)
376 vs genotype (PR+ and PR- neurons), using the Sidak test to correct for multiple
377 comparisons. In Figure 5E, a two-way ANOVA, with Sidak test for multiple comparisons,
378 was used to investigate the origin of the differences in the location factor that were
379 specific for PR- neurons. In the properties whose residuals did not pass the normality
380 test, a logarithmic or square root transformation was applied and normality was
381 consequently reassessed. As specified in the legend, in the properties that the
382 transformations did not make the residuals become normally distributed, we performed
383 a Kruskal-Wallis test followed by a Dunn's post-hoc test for multiple comparisons.
384 For Figure 2A-F, a Mixed-effects test with repeated measures, and Figure 7C-H a two-
385 way ANOVA with repeated measures were performed. For Figure 1E-F and 5B and C a
386 Chi-square test was performed, the pairwise comparisons we tested followed the same
387 structure as the one obtained for the three-way ANOVA multiple comparisons. Whisker
388 plots represent median with interquartile range. Error bars represent mean \pm SEM. p
389 values were rounded to two decimal places. Significance was noted as * $p < 0.05$,
390 ** $p < 0.01$.

391 **Results**

392 **The proportion of tonic and phasic firing PR+ neurons varies across the antero-** 393 **posterior axis.**

394 In order to investigate the neuronal excitability of PR+ and PR- neurons, we recorded
395 current to voltage input-output response curves (I-V curves) at resting potential in
396 current-clamp mode in acute slices of naturally cycling PR-Cre x EYFP adult female

397 mice. Briefly, the female reproductive stage was determined by vaginal lavage and
398 slices were obtained from females in the least receptive state (diestrus) and the most
399 receptive state (proestrus/estrus). PR+ neurons were identified by their natural
400 fluorescence under the microscope and PR- by the absence of fluorescence (see
401 Methods for details).

402 We performed a PCA-initialized t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (tSNE)
403 analysis on the I-V curve firing rates obtained for our full sample of recorded PR+ and
404 PR- neurons. To understand how many clusters can be optimally distinguished in the
405 resulting embedded data (Fig. 1A), we performed k-means clustering with a possible
406 number of clusters varying between one and eight. When quantifying the sum of
407 squared distances between each datapoint and its assigned cluster centroid over an
408 increasing number of clusters, we observed a characteristic “elbow” shape when there
409 were three possible clusters, suggesting this is the optimal number of clusters in our
410 dataset (Fig. 1B). The first two clusters corresponded to tonic neurons with high and low
411 firing rates (Fig. 1A, A1 and A2, respectively). Tonic firing neurons exhibited a linear
412 increase in firing rate in response to the increases in the magnitude of current injected
413 (Fig. 1C, top). The third cluster roughly corresponded to phasic firing neurons (Fig. 1A,
414 A3), neurons in which the action potentials did not linearly increase in response to
415 increased current injection (Fig. 1C, bottom). These neurons exhibited a step function-
416 like behavior, where after reaching the firing threshold, the number of action potentials
417 remained constant with increased amounts of current. However, when visually
418 inspecting the firing profiles of neurons in this cluster (Fig. 1C), we observed that this
419 cluster included phasic neurons and neurons in which the firing rate initially increased

420 linearly but then entered depolarization block and drastically reduced their firing rate
421 (Fig. 1A, A4). When dividing the peak firing rate of each neuron by their firing rate at the
422 maximum current injected (240pA), a subset of neurons with particularly high ratio
423 values was clearly distinguishable from the rest (Fig. 1D). These neurons were tonic
424 firing neurons with depolarization block.

425 We therefore considered two major categories of neurons. The first category being tonic
426 firing neurons, comprising neurons that did not reach the depolarization block within the
427 range of currents we injected (Fig. 1A1 and A2, tonic neurons), and neurons that did
428 (Fig. 1A4, tonic neurons with depolarization block), independently of their firing rate.
429 And the second category being phasic firing neurons (Fig. 1A3).

430 The majority of the anterior and medial PR+ neurons displayed tonic firing, while most of
431 the posterior ones displayed phasic firing (Fig. 1E, Chi-square test, $p < 0.001$), with no
432 differences across the reproductive cycle. In contrast, the PR- population is
433 homogenously composed of a higher proportion of tonic firing neurons across the AP
434 axis (Fig. 1F).

435 To summarize, the VMHvl is composed of multiple electrophysiological phenotypes and
436 posterior PR+ neurons have a higher density of phasic neurons in comparison to the
437 anterior and medial levels of the VMHvl.

438

439 **Local changes in the intrinsic excitability and threshold to spike of PR+ neurons**
440 **across the reproductive cycle.**

441

442 The analysis of the I-V curves revealed that in the anterior and posterior VMHvl, the
443 excitability of PR+ neurons does not to change across the cycle (Fig. 2A and C). In
444 contrast, medial PR+ neurons of non-receptive females showed significantly higher
445 excitability when compared to the excitability of medial PR+ neurons originating from
446 receptive females, particularly in response to higher input current (Fig. 2B, top, strong
447 interaction between the phase of the cycle and the amount of current injected (Mixed-
448 effects test, $F(8, 160)=6.87$, $p<0.0001$)). This modulation is caused by a change in the
449 excitability of the tonic firing medial neurons across the reproductive cycle while the
450 behavior of medial phasic neurons remained unchanged (Fig. 2B, bottom). In addition,
451 this change was specific to the PR+ population since no changes were observed across
452 the cycle in the PR- neurons at any of the AP levels (Fig. 2D-F).

453

454 We also observed that the PR+ population was less excitable than the PR- in the
455 anterior and posterior levels of the VMHvl (Mixed-effects test, ant PR+ vs ant PR- $F(8,$
456 $360)=3.53$, $p<0.001$ and post PR+ vs post PR- $F(8, 361)=2.83$, $p<0.01$) but not in the
457 medial subdivision, probably in part due to the increased excitability of medial PR+
458 neurons from non-receptive females.

459 It is worth mentioning that the membrane resistance did not vary across experimental
460 groups (Table 1) and only a small decrease was observed in the capacitance of the
461 anterior and posterior PR+ of non-receptive females (three-way ANOVA, location/phase
462 interaction $F(2, 132)=3.20$, $p=0.04$). The membrane time constant (τ) also did not vary
463 across the reproductive cycle, however posterior PR+ neurons exhibited a smaller τ

464 when compared to the anterior PR+ population (three-way ANOVA, location $F(2,$
465 $132)=3.23$, $p=0.04$, multiple comparison ant vs pos $p=0.04$).

466 The resting potential of anterior PR+ neurons of receptive females was lower when
467 compared to non-receptive females (Fig. 3A and B, three-way ANOVA, phase
468 $F(1,132)=6.39$, $p=0.01$, multiple comparison antNon-Rec vs antRec $p<0.01$). However,
469 this difference was not large enough to produce changes in the threshold to spike (Fig.
470 3C). The latency to spike of PR+ and PR- neurons did not vary across the cycle (Fig. 3F
471 and H). In addition, we observed a mild, yet significant, lower latency to spike of the
472 posterior neurons when compared to anterior (Fig. 3F and H, three-way ANOVA,
473 location $F(2,132)=5.48$, $p<0.01$, multiple comparison ant vs pos $p=0.01$) and medial
474 neurons (multiple comparison med vs pos $p=0.01$) that was independent of the phase of
475 the cycle and the genotype.

476 The regularity of the recorded spike trains was similar across experimental groups, as
477 shown by comparable CV2 values across phase and location for both the PR+ and PR-
478 populations (regularity was determined at 150pA of injected current, Fig. 3G and I).

479

480 In focusing on the action potential shape, we observed a comparable amplitude and
481 half-width of the action potentials across the reproductive cycle in PR+ and PR- neurons
482 (Fig. 4A-E). The spike amplitude of the posterior neurons of both PR+ and PR-
483 populations is moderately but consistently smaller compared to anterior neurons (Fig.
484 4B and D, three-way ANOVA, location $F(2,132)=5.74$, $p<0.01$, multiple comparison ant
485 vs pos $p=0.03$) and medial (multiple comparison med vs pos $p<0.01$).

486

487 Together, these results suggest that the electrophysiological properties of VMHvl
488 neurons vary across the reproductive cycle, but the observed changes depend on their
489 location in the AP axis. In the sexually receptive phase, anterior PR+ neurons are more
490 hyperpolarized in their resting state and the medial PR+ population exhibits lower
491 excitability.

492

493 **The anterior VMHvl presents a higher proportion of rebound firing neurons during**
494 **the non-sexually receptive phase of the cycle.**

495 Finally, and given that it is well established that hyperpolarizing input can trigger
496 rebound depolarizing responses increasing the firing rate of neurons in a wide variety of
497 brain areas including the hypothalamus (Burdakov et al., 2004; Israel et al., 2008), we
498 sought to characterize the response of VMHvl neurons to hyperpolarizing input. To do
499 so, we quantified the proportion of VMHvl neurons which exhibited rebound firing after
500 hyperpolarization (Fig. 5A, -90pA for 1s). We observed that 6 out of 32 PR+ neurons of
501 non-receptive females and only 2 out of 38 PR+ neurons of receptive females fired
502 rebound action potentials (Fig. 5B). This difference originates mainly from the anterior
503 PR+ neurons (chi-square test, antNon-Rec+ vs antRec+ $p=0.01$), where 4 out of 11
504 neurons of non-receptive females displayed rebound firing while in receptive females
505 none of the 13 recorded neurons produced rebound action potentials. Furthermore, no
506 significant differences were observed between PR+ neurons across the AP axis nor
507 between the PR+ and the PR- populations (Fig. 5B and 5C).

508 Rebound depolarization is caused by the hyperpolarization activated inward current (I_h)
509 which represents a powerful modulator of neuronal firing frequency and timing (Momin

510 et al., 2008). Thus, we quantified the Ih current amplitude in VMHvl neurons (Fig. 5D
511 and E). A significant difference was obtained in the interaction between location and
512 genotype (three-way ANOVA, location/genotype interaction $F(2, 132)=4.36$ $p=0.01$), that
513 however, was not large enough to yield statistical differences across groups in the
514 multiple comparisons test. To pinpoint the origin of such changes, we analyzed
515 separately PR+ and PR- populations. Our results show that while the Ih magnitude was
516 unchanged across the AP axis for the PR+ population, the anterior PR- neurons have
517 modestly higher Ih magnitude compared to medial and posterior PR- neurons (Two-way
518 ANOVA, location $F(2,68)=6.30$, $p<0.01$, multiple comparison ant vs med $p=0.04$, ant vs
519 pos $p<0.01$), however, these differences are not reflected in a significantly different
520 fraction of rebound anterior PR- neurons compared medial and posterior PR- neurons
521 (Fig. 5C).

522 To summarize, the proportion of neurons with rebound firing is fairly homogenous in the
523 VMHvl across the reproductive cycle and independently of genotype, with the exception
524 of its most anterior subdivision, where PR+ neurons exhibit cyclical alterations. Given
525 that these changes are not accompanied by a modulation of Ih current, they likely reflect
526 the change in resting membrane potential that drives receptive neurons away from their
527 firing threshold, causing Ih mediated depolarization to fail to produce rebound firing (Fig.
528 3B, Fig. 5A).

529

530 **Localized structural plasticity of VMHvl PR+ neurons across the reproductive**
531 **cycle.**

532 To study the impact of the phase of the reproductive cycle on the morphological
533 properties of VMHvl neurons, we reconstructed and performed morphometric
534 quantifications of the soma area, number of dendrites, primary dendrites and branch
535 points per neuron of PR+ and PR- neurons in different locations across the AP axis of
536 the VMHvl. As previously reported, the VMHvl is primarily composed of glutamatergic
537 neurons, that are surrounded by GABAergic neurons (Yamamoto et al 2018). In fact,
538 the absence of GABAergic somas has been used to delineate the boundaries of the
539 VMH (Jarvie & Hentges, 2012). Taking advantage of mice expressing the fluorescent
540 reporter tdTomato under the promoter of the vesicular transporter of GABA (VGat-
541 tdTomato) (Kaneko et al., 2018) we observed, as expected, lower signal intensity inside
542 the boundaries of the VMH (Fig. 6A) that was consistent across the AP regions of the
543 VMH. The limits obtained with the inspection of GABAergic markers were used to
544 delineate the boundaries of the VMHvl, and ensure that the neurons characterized in
545 this study were indeed within the nucleus (Fig. 6B and C).

546

547 The somatic area was unaltered across the reproductive cycle and was not different
548 between the PR+ and PR- populations (Table 2). We observed that PR+ neurons of
549 receptive females exhibit a robust increase in the number of dendrites per neuron
550 across the AP axis (Table 2, three-way ANOVA, genotype/phase interaction $F(1, 173)=7.85$, $p=0.01$), and a higher number of branching points per neuron compared to
551 neurons originating from non-receptive females (Table 2, three-way ANOVA,
552 genotype/phase interaction $F(1, 173)=5.81$, $p=0.02$). The changes across the
553 reproductive cycle are specific for the PR+ population, as they were not observed in PR-

555 neurons (Table 2). Both in medial PR+ and PR- neurons, independent of the phase of
556 the cycle, we observed a moderately lower number of primary dendrites per neuron,
557 compared to the anterior and posterior neurons which yielded small yet significant
558 differences across the AP axis (three-way ANOVA, location $F(2, 173)=3.14$, $p=0.04$).

559 Neurons in the VMHvl are characterized by having a long primary dendrite (LPD) that
560 can be several fold longer than its short primary dendrites (SPD) (Calizo & Flanagan-
561 cato, 2002). Therefore, we analyzed LPD and SPD separately (Table 2). While the
562 length of the LPD of PR+ was unchanged across the reproductive cycle, PR- neurons
563 exhibited longer LPDs in non-receptive females (three-way ANOVA, genotype/phase
564 interaction $F(1, 168)=6.67$, $p=0.01$). No overall significant differences were found in the
565 SPD length of PR+ and PR- neurons across the cycle and AP axis. Interestingly, the
566 posterior neurons were shown to have shorter LPDs than the anterior and medial
567 neurons regardless of the phase of the cycle or the genotype (three-way ANOVA,
568 location $F(2, 168)=9.73$, $p<0.0001$). No differences in the length of LPDs and SPDs
569 were found between the PR+ and PR- populations.

570 In addition to the analysis of dendritic length, we sought to investigate whether the
571 complexity of the dendritic trees was modified across the reproductive cycle. To do so,
572 we used the Sholl method that measures the number of dendritic processes
573 intersections as a function of the radial distance from the soma. No changes were
574 observed in the maximum number of dendritic intersections of PR+ and PR- neurons
575 across the phase of the cycle (Fig. 7A-H) nor across their location in the VMHvl,
576 indicating that these neurons reach comparable maximum complexities in their dendritic
577 trees. Nevertheless, the analysis of the Sholl profiles of these neurons revealed that the

578 posterior PR+ neurons of non-receptive females had a significantly lower complexity of
579 their dendritic tree (Fig. 7E, repeated measures ANOVA $p < 0.0001$) compared to those
580 from females in the receptive phase. In addition, the medial PR- neurons of non-
581 receptive females had a higher complexity than their counterparts in receptive females
582 (Fig. 7G, repeated measures ANOVA $F(40, 136) = 3.10$, $p < 0.0001$).

583 The increased complexity observed in the posterior PR+ neurons of females in the
584 receptive phase was large enough to provide differences when tested with the same
585 method specifically in the proximal branching (Fig. 7E, $< 250\mu\text{m}$ from the soma), while
586 the increased complexity of the medial PR- neurons of non-receptive females were
587 observed at more distal parts of the soma (240 to $340\mu\text{m}$) and were large enough to
588 yield multiple comparisons significant changes (Fig. 7G).

589 We also observed that medial PR+ neurons have lower dendritic branching than medial
590 PR- neurons (Fig. 7G, repeated measures ANOVA $F(35, 2030) = 2.84$, $p < 0.0001$),
591 particularly in the distal parts from the soma (320 to $380\mu\text{m}$). The posterior PR+
592 neurons have lower proximal dendritic branching than the posterior PR- neurons (Fig.
593 7H, repeated measures ANOVA $F(40, 2520) = 1.77$, $p < 0.01$). These observations
594 indicate that PR+ neurons have a different dendritic complexity proximal to the cell body
595 compared to that of the PR- population, independent of the phase of the reproductive
596 cycle.

597 To summarize, similarly to what we report for the electrophysiological properties, the
598 structural properties of PR+ and PR- neurons are diverse, with some varying across the
599 AP axis and the reproductive cycle.

600 **Dendritic spine density largely differs between the PR+ and PR- populations.**

601 Previous studies have shown that externally primed estrogen exerts effects on the
602 dendritic spine density of VMHvl neurons that are different depending on the type of
603 dendrite, specifically, an increase in spine density on SPDs of VMHvl neurons (Calizo &
604 Flanagan-cato, 2000) and a decrease of the spine density on LPDs of VMHvl neurons
605 expressing the receptor for estrogen (Calizo & Flanagan-cato, 2002). In order to
606 determine if such modulation of the spine density of VMHvl neurons is present in the
607 physiological range of sex hormone fluctuation, the dendritic spine density of PR+ and
608 PR- neurons was analyzed depending not only on their location in the VMHvl, but also
609 on the primary dendrite category across the reproductive cycle of naturally cycling
610 females. Although overall PR+ and PR- neurons have comparable spine densities on
611 SPDs across the reproductive cycle (Fig. 8A and C) and location, posterior VMHvl
612 neurons in non- receptive females have higher spine density on SPDs compared to
613 posterior VMHvl neurons in the receptive phase resulting in a significant interaction
614 between the phase of the cycle and location within the VMHvl (three-way ANOVA,
615 phase/location interaction $F(2,153)=3.88$, $p=0.02$). Furthermore, the PR+ population has
616 significantly lower spine density on the SPDs than PR- neurons (Fig. 8E, three-way
617 ANOVA, genotype $F(1, 153)=26.21$, $p<0.01$).

618 Similar to what was observed for the spine densities of SPDs, for LPDs we observed
619 that the posterior VMHvl neurons of receptive females present a decreased spine
620 density compared to posterior neurons from females that were non-receptive, which in
621 the case of LPDs the change is specific to PR+ neurons (Fig. 8B and D, three-way

622 ANOVA, phase/location/genotype interaction $F(2, 150)=4.81$, $p=0.01$, multiple
623 comparison posNon-Rec+ vs posRec+, $p=0.01$).

624 In addition, by comparing PR+ with PR- neurons, we observed that PR+ neurons have
625 lower spine density on the LPDs (Fig. 8F, three-way ANOVA, genotype $F(1, 150)=7.25$,
626 $p=0.01$).

627 Altogether, we observed that neurons expressing progesterone receptor have an overall
628 lower spine density when compared to their neighboring PR- neurons. Across the
629 reproductive cycle, posterior PR+ neurons undergo more pronounced structural
630 changes, exhibiting even lower spine density in the receptive phase.

631

632 **Discussion**

633 We combined whole-cell recordings with labeling of individual neurons to investigate the
634 structural and electrophysiological properties of PR+ and PR- neurons along the AP
635 axis of the VMHvl and across the reproductive cycle of naturally cycling female mice.
636 First, we report the existence of multiple electrophysiological phenotypes within the
637 VMHvl, including tonic firing neurons (with and without depolarization block) and phasic
638 firing neurons. We show that PR+ cells are distinct from PR- in three major aspects:
639 first, due to structural properties (PR+ neurons have lower spine densities in general);
640 second, due to the great extent to which the properties of PR+ neurons vary across the
641 AP axis; and third due to local changes in the properties of PR+ across the reproductive
642 cycle (which are minimal for the PR- population). Our results further support the

643 existence of subdivisions in the VMHvl and its possible role in coordinating female
644 behavior with the internal reproductive state.

645 The impact of the reproductive cycle on VMHvl function has been interrogated *in vivo*
646 and *in vitro*, but most studies were performed in females whose ovaries were removed
647 and then supplemented with estrogen and progesterone (Calizo & Flanagan-cato, 2000,
648 2002; Griffin et al., 2010; Griffin & Flanagan-Cato, 2008; Millhouse, 1973; Rubin &
649 Barfield, 1980, 1983b, 1983a, but see Inoue et al., 2019; Nomoto & Lima, 2015, for
650 examples of naturally cycling studies). While these manipulations are convenient,
651 easing experimental planning and decreasing interindividual variability (with the extra
652 benefit of allowing a reduction in the number of females used), ovariectomized females
653 with hormonal replacement differ substantially from intact females: first, before
654 hormonal replacement the levels of sex hormones are extremely low, as the main
655 source of estrogen and progesterone is absent and second because the hormonal
656 treatment exposes females to concentrations of sex hormones that differ from
657 physiological levels (Liu & Shi, 2015). The expression of hormone receptors, such as
658 the progesterone receptor, are under the control of sex hormone levels as well
659 (MacLusky & McEwen, 1978), meaning that that the neuronal response is affected at
660 the level of the receiver (receptor) and message (sex hormone). Persistent hormonal
661 replacement of ovariectomized females leads to tumor development (Kordon et al.,
662 1993) further suggesting that the hormonal treatment leads to undesired physiological
663 effects. Finally, the sexual behavior that hormonally treated females exhibits differs from
664 the behavior of naturally cycling females (Zipse et al., 2000), suggesting that the
665 treatment fails to fully recapitulate the effects of natural sex hormones levels. To the

666 best of our knowledge, this is the first study interrogating the intrinsic properties of
667 neurons across the reproductive cycle of naturally cycling females and therefore the
668 results observed reflect endogenous changes. However, we cannot claim that the
669 changes we observe across the reproductive cycle are an effect of sex hormone levels
670 because those were not directly manipulated. Manipulations with more naturalistic
671 levels of sex hormones or local manipulations in the expression levels of sex hormone
672 receptors should be employed to establish a direct causal link between hormonal levels,
673 the structural and physiological properties of VMHvl neurons and the changes
674 observed.

675 In the present study we report, for the first time, the existence of different neuronal types
676 in the VMHvl according to their firing pattern. We found tonic and phasic neurons, in
677 both PR+ and PR- populations, intermingled across the AP axis of the VMHvl. However,
678 the presence of phasic neurons was particularly abundant in the posterior VMHvl, where
679 it comprised more than half of the recorded PR+ neurons.

680 This AP gradient may have strong implications not only for the role of different portions
681 of the VMHvl in controlling behavioral output, but also for the interpretation of activity
682 manipulations, such as the optogenetic control of neural activity. While anterior VMHvl
683 neurons can reach high firing frequencies, posterior phasic neurons present a robust
684 stop of action potential generation after reaching the spiking threshold that does not
685 depend on the current injected in the cell. Importantly, this may be particularly relevant
686 for the interpretation of results where different laser intensities produce diverse
687 behavioral outputs (Kunwar et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2014), as optogenetic activation at

688 particular AP levels may bias the activation of neuronal populations with different
689 intrinsic properties.

690 Other hypothalamic neuronal populations, such as the tuberoinfundibular dopamine
691 neurons (Lyons et al., 2012) or the gonadotropin-releasing hormone neurons (Jarry et
692 al., 1991) present in the tuberal and preoptic hypothalamus, are known to display phasic
693 firing behavior. Furthermore, the presence of intermingled tonic and phasic firing
694 neuronal population has been previously reported in the magnocellular nucleus of the
695 hypothalamus (Israel et al., 2016), where oxytocin neurons show tonic and vasopressin
696 neurons phasic firing behavior. The differential role of tonic and phasic firing neurons in
697 the control of goal directed behaviors (Budygin et al., 2020; Grace et al., 2007) but also
698 in their contributions for encoding stimulus-environment features (Pilkiw et al., 2017)
699 has been widely studied throughout the brain. In addition, it is known that changes in
700 voltage sensitive channels (Suzuki & Rogawskit, 1989), that can be triggered by
701 neuromodulation (Lyons et al., 2012; Valentino & Van Bockstaele, 2015), are able to
702 mediate the dynamic transition between tonic to phasic firing regimes. In the VMHvl,
703 whether tonic and phasic firing neuronal populations, or the dynamic transition between
704 these firing regimes, contribute to different aspects of socio-sexual behavior remains
705 elusive and should be the focus of future studies.

706 Our results indicate that PR+ cells are distinct from their neighbors, a difference that is
707 probably established early in development, and later on by the fact that their intrinsic
708 properties of this population can be directly affected by estrogen and progesterone, as
709 PR+ neurons co-express estrogen receptor (Blaustein & Turcotte, 1985; Hashikawa et
710 al., 2017; Sá & Fonseca, 2017). Interestingly, the properties of PR- neurons were

711 similar along the AP axis and across the reproductive cycle, with the exception of
712 changes in the dendritic complexity of neurons in the medial VMHvl. This observation
713 may be explained by the fact that not all ER+ neurons co-express progesterone
714 receptor. ER+/PR- neurons were not labeled with our genetic strategy, but their
715 properties are sensitive to fluctuating levels of estrogen (Calizo & Flanagan-cato, 2000,
716 2002). Intersectional strategies are needed to address this question.

717 Interestingly, even though anterior PR+ neurons had a comparable excitability profile
718 across the reproductive cycle, the resting potential of neurons in the receptive phase
719 was significantly hyperpolarized. This change in resting potential likely underlies a
720 moderate increase in the threshold to fire in these neurons, which required more current
721 to start generating action potentials. Even if this trend did not reach significant
722 differences with our current statistical power, the visual difference between anterior non-
723 receptive and receptive PR+ neurons can hardly be overlooked (Fig. 3C). In addition,
724 the anterior PR+ neurons of receptive females do not show hyperpolarized-induced
725 rebound firing. The fact that these neurons have a more hyperpolarized resting
726 potential, thus more distant from the firing threshold, might explain the fact that the
727 same magnitude of Ih current fails to evoke rebound firing in anterior PR+ at the
728 receptive phase (Fig. 5B). We also report a robust increase of the firing rate under
729 same current injections in medial VMHvl neurons obtained from females in the non-
730 receptive phase compared to those in the receptive phase. These changes were not
731 accompanied by changes in capacitance or membrane resistance across the
732 reproductive cycle of medial neurons, thus it is unlikely that the changes in firing rate
733 are caused by differences in the passive propagation of current into the neuron and

734 instead points towards a modulation of voltage sensitive channels in the medial PR+
735 neurons, that may be mediated by progesterone (Scharfman & MacLusky, 2006).
736 Overall, these results suggest that the anterior and medial VMHvl have the potential to
737 generate more action potentials in non-receptive females, which is in seeming
738 disagreement with the enhanced-male evoked responses that we previously observed,
739 at the population level, in the VMHvl of sexually receptive female mice (Nomoto & Lima,
740 2015). However, the results of this study were obtained with extracellular recordings of
741 non-identified neurons and therefore we do not know if they were PR+ or PR-. Also, in
742 the present study, we investigated the intrinsic properties of VMHvl neurons and cannot
743 make any claim regarding the driving input they receive (synaptic and/or
744 neuromodulatory). The VMHvl receives indirect input from the vomeronasal organ,
745 which includes some neurons whose activity is increased in response to male stimuli
746 when females are sexually receptive (Dey et al., 2015). It is conceivable that the
747 enhanced VMHvl activity that we previously observed reflects modifications at the
748 sensory level.

749 It has been previously reported that hormonal treatment in ovariectomized rats reduced
750 the amount and length of secondary dendrites of a non-defined VMHvl neuronal
751 population (Griffin & Flanagan-cato, 2009). Even if in seeming contradiction with our
752 findings, since we report the opposite effect in dendritic complexity and unchanged
753 dendritic lengths, we would like to point out several possible reasons for such
754 difference. First, the changes we observed are specific to the posterior PR+ population
755 (and absent in our sample of PR- neurons), therefore, sampling VMHvl neurons
756 independently of their genotype could have masked a specific plasticity process in

757 posterior PR+ neurons. Second, in our dataset we observed that medial PR- neurons
758 undergo a reduction in dendritic complexity that goes in line with previous reports. Thus,
759 pooling samples from different levels of the VMHvl may mask changes, or alternatively
760 sampling exclusively in a single AP region of the VMHvl could lead to findings that are
761 limited to that level alone, and thus not generalizable to the whole VMHvl. Interestingly,
762 posterior PR+ neurons did not only undergo changes at the level of their dendritic
763 complexity, but also at the level of spine density, which was reduced in the receptive
764 phase specifically in their LPDs. The fact that such dendritic spine changes are specific
765 to LPDs may suggest that some pathway specific plasticity is happening during the
766 reproductive cycle. Even though it has been previously hypothesized that SPDs may
767 preferentially integrate local excitatory inputs, while LPDs may preferentially interact
768 with long range inputs, inhibitory neurons of the shell and neuropeptides (Griffin &
769 Flanagan-cato, 2011; Yamamoto et al., 2018), as of yet, no circuit mapping study has
770 quantitatively explored what is the anatomical origin of the inputs. Thus, both the
771 anatomical origin of those inputs and their possible relevance for the dendritic coding
772 presented here needs to be further investigated. Our findings suggest a modification of
773 the overall synaptic weights that the LPDs and SPDs will have in the dendritic
774 integration for output generation, with a bias towards the inputs contacting SPDs.

775 It is worth noting that while the spine densities we observed are comparable to the ones
776 reported in previous studies (Calizo & Flanagan-cato, 2002), the dendritic lengths we
777 report both for PR+ and for PR- neurons are several fold longer than those previously
778 reported (Calizo & Flanagan-cato, 2002). These changes may be explained by the
779 differences in the technical approaches used to investigate neuronal structure. While

780 previous reports have used fixed histological slices (100-150 microns) filled *a posteriori*
781 with lucifer yellow, in the present study we have used acute slices for *ex vivo*
782 electrophysiological recordings (300 microns), in which neurons were filled with biocytin
783 during their electrophysiological monitoring. Thus, several key differences may explain
784 the contradictory results: first, the thickness of the slice, which could allow us to track
785 dendrites for longer extensions; second, the fact that neurons in acute slices for *ex vivo*
786 recordings reseal their membranes, producing a visible thickening in the extremity of
787 their cut dendrites, thus allowing us to recognize incomplete dendrites with our technical
788 approach.

789 In summary, we have observed a **multiple electrophysiological phenotypes within**
790 **the VMHvl and a** surprising diversity of structural and physiological plasticity processes
791 both along the AP axis of the VMHvl, and across the reproductive cycle, within the
792 genetically defined population of PR+ cells. These findings highlight the repertoire of
793 local plasticity rules across the VMHvl that is probably explained by the different
794 specialized transcriptomic clusters previously characterized across the AP extension of
795 the VMHvl (Kim et al., 2019; McClellan et al., 2006), supporting the existence of
796 subdivisions in the VMHvl and a more complex role of this hypothalamic structure in
797 socio-sexual behavior, which has been recently acknowledged (Hashikawa et al., 2017;
798 Inoue et al., 2019; Sakurai et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2013). The
799 existence of multiple subdivisions that undergo local changes in response to sex
800 hormone levels hint to the hypothesis that this hypothalamic structure might be able to
801 control a complex and coordinated set of responses in reaction to an ubiquitous
802 message, the systemic levels of sex hormones in circulation, from metabolism to sexual

803 receptivity. This idea is supported by the connectivity of ER+ neurons, which present a
804 high degree of output divergence, with anterior ER+ neurons projecting to pre-motor
805 areas, while posterior ER+ are engaged in amygdalo-hypothalamic loops (Lo et al.,
806 2019). Similar circuit motifs have been described in other hypothalamic nuclei, such as
807 the organum vasculosum of the lamina terminalis (OVLT), where different subnuclei can
808 coordinate a multipronged response in reaction to thirst (Graebner et al., 2015).
809 Altogether, it becomes evident that acknowledging the different neuronal properties
810 within the AP axis of the VMHvl is crucial to have a holistic understanding of its
811 involvement in behavior and further studies with focal manipulations are needed to
812 understand the functional role of observed local properties and their modulation by the
813 reproductive cycle.

814

815 **Legends**

816 **Figure 1 - The predominant firing pattern of PR+ neurons varies across the AP**
817 **axis and differs from the PR- population.**

818 (A) Low-dimensional embedding of VMHvl neurons Input current to output voltage
819 responses (IV curves) using tSNE. Four representative examples of the different firing
820 responses found correspond to tonic neurons with high firing rate (A1), tonic neurons
821 with low firing rate (A2), phasic neurons (A3), and tonic neurons with depolarization
822 block (A4). (B) Sum of squared distances between each data point and its assigned
823 cluster as a function of increasing number of possible clusters. (C,D) Tonic neurons
824 with depolarization block, that initially were largely clustered with the phasic neurons,
825 can be distinguished by obtaining the ratio between the maximum firing rate and the
826 firing rate at the maximum current injected (240pA). (E) The majority of PR+ neurons in
827 the anterior and medial VMHvl display tonic firing, while the posterior PR+ neurons have
828 mainly phasic firing ($p < 0.001$), with no changes across the reproductive cycle. (F) The
829 PR- neurons display mainly tonic firing across the whole AP axis and do not change
830 across the reproductive cycle. Chi-square test. $**p < 0.01$

831

832 **Figure 2 - The excitability of medial PR+ neurons changes across the**
833 **reproductive cycle.**

834 (A-C) Top: Group mean and SEM of Input-output (IV) curves across the reproductive
835 cycle reporting the firing frequency of PR+ neurons after injecting 1000ms current

836 pulses between 0 and 240pA (30pA steps), reporting changes only in (B) medial PR+
837 neurons ($F(8, 160)=6.87$, $p<0.0001$, multiple comparison $p=0.02$ at 180pA, $p<0.01$ at
838 210pA, $p<0.001$ at 240pA). Bottom: Mean of tonic and phasic firing responses per
839 group. Insets: representative recordings of voltage response from PR+ neurons in
840 response to the same current injection. Anterior $n=11$ NR, $n=13$ R, Medial $n=11$ NR,
841 $n=12$ R, Posterior $n=10$ NR, $n=13$ R. (D-F) Input-output (IV) curves across the
842 reproductive cycle reporting no changes in the firing frequency of PR- neurons after
843 injecting 1000ms current pulses between 0 and 240pA (30pA steps). Insets:
844 representative recordings of voltage response from PR- neurons in response to the
845 same current injection. Anterior $n=15$ NR, $n=11$ R, Medial $n=10$ NR, $n=13$ R, Posterior
846 $n=12$ NR, $n=13$ R. (A,C,D,F) PR+ neurons are less excitable than PR- in the anterior
847 and posterior VMHvl ($F(8, 360)=3.53$, $p<0.001$ and $F(8, 361)=2.83$, $p<0.01$,
848 respectively) but not in (B,E) the medial. Mixed-effects test with repeated measures.
849 Mean (\pm SEM). * $p<0.05$

850

851 **Table 1 - Passive membrane properties of the PR+ and PR- populations across**
852 **the reproductive cycle and the AP axis.**

853 Capacitance: L1*- location/phase interaction $F(2, 132)=3.20$, $p=0.04$; τ : L2*- location
854 $F(2, 132)=3.23$, $p=0.04$. Three-way ANOVA, Sidak correction for multiple comparison.
855 Values expressed as Median (IQR). * $p<0.05$

856 T-Tonic neurons; P-Phasic neurons. Values expressed as Median.

857

858 **Figure 3 – The resting membrane potential of anterior PR+ neurons changes**
859 **across the reproductive cycle.**

860 (A) Representative membrane voltage recordings from PR+ neurons in response to 30
861 and 90pA. (B) Anterior PR+ neurons of receptive females have a lower resting potential
862 compared to non-receptive females (phase $F(1,130)=6.39$, $p=0.01$, multiple comparison
863 antNon-Rec+ vs antRec+ $p<0.01$). (C) The threshold to spike, (F) Latency to spike and
864 (G) Regularity of the spike train (CV2) of the PR+ neurons do not change. Anterior $n=11$
865 NR, $n=13$ R, Medial $n=11$ NR, $n=12$ R, Posterior $n=10$ NR, $n=13$ R. (D) Resting
866 potential, (E) Threshold to spike, (H) Latency to spike and (I) Regularity of the spike
867 train (CV2) do not vary in PR- neurons across the reproductive cycle. Anterior $n=15$ NR,
868 $n=11$ R, Medial $n=10$ NR, $n=13$ R, Posterior $n=12$ NR, $n=13$ R. (F, H) There is a mild
869 lower latency to spike of the posterior neurons independently of the cycle and genotype
870 (location $F(2, 132)=5.48$, $p=0.01$, L^* - multiple comparison ant vs pos $p=0.01$ and med
871 vs pos $p=0.01$). (B, D, F, H) Three-way ANOVA, Sidak correction for multiple
872 comparison. (C, E, G, I) Kruskal-Wallis test, with multiple comparisons. Box plots
873 represent medians (\pm 25-75 percentile). * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$. Individual data points are
874 shown per group color coded according their tonic or phasic firing type.

875

876 **Figure 4 - The spike waveform of PR+ and PR- neurons is consistent across the**
877 **reproductive cycle.**

878 (A) Illustration of the recording protocol used to quantify action potential properties and
879 representative examples of the average spike waveform illustrating the amplitude and

880 the half-width (HW). (B, D) The amplitude of the first action potential for each current
881 injection step of the PR+ and PR- neurons does not change across the reproductive
882 cycle, however it differs mildly across the AP axis (location $F(2, 132)=5.74$, $p<0.01$,
883 multiple comparison L^* - ant vs pos $p=0.03$ and L^{**} - med vs pos $p<0.01$). (C, E) The
884 spike half-width of PR+ and PR- neurons is consistent across the reproductive cycle
885 and the AP axis. PR+ Anterior $n=11$ NR, $n=13$ R, Medial $n=11$ NR, $n=12$ R, Posterior
886 $n=10$ NR, $n=13$ R. PR- Anterior $n=15$ NR, $n=11$ R, Medial $n=10$ NR, $n=13$ R, Posterior
887 $n=12$ NR, $n=13$ R. Three-way ANOVA, Sidak correction for multiple comparison.
888 Medians (\pm 25-75 percentile). * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$. Individual data points are shown per
889 group color coded according their tonic or phasic firing type.

890

891 **Figure 5 - The proportion of anterior PR+ neurons with rebound firing changes**
892 **across the reproductive cycle.**

893 (A) Example of recordings of voltage response at -90 pA. Proportion of neurons
894 presenting rebound firing after hyperpolarization of (B) PR+ neurons from non-receptive
895 and receptive females, and from (C) PR- neurons from non-receptive and receptive
896 females. The anterior PR+ neurons of non-receptive females display a significantly
897 higher fraction of neurons with rebound spikes compared to receptive females ($p=0.01$)
898 Chi-square test. (D) The lh amplitude of the PR+ neurons does not change across the
899 reproductive cycle nor the AP axis, while the (E) lh amplitude of PR- neurons varies
900 across the AP axis (three-way ANOVA location/genotype interaction $F(2, 132)=4.36$
901 $p=0.01$, two-way ANOVA for PR-, location $F(2,68)=6.30$, $p<0.01$, multiple comparison L^*

902 - ant vs med $p=0.04$, L** - ant vs pos $p<0.01$). Three-way ANOVA and (E) Two-way,
903 Sidak correction for multiple comparison. * $p<0.05$. Individual data points are shown per
904 group color coded according their tonic or phasic firing type.

905

906 **Figure 6 – Localization of reconstructed PR+ and PR- neurons across the VMHvl.**

907 (A) Limits of the VMH obtained with the inspection of GABAergic markers across the AP
908 axis. Schematic representation of the reconstructed PR+ Anterior $n=19$ NR, $n=15$ R,
909 Medial $n=17$ NR, $n=19$ R, Posterior $n=20$ NR, $n=16$ R. (B) and PR- Anterior $n=16$ NR,
910 $n=10$ R, Medial $n=12$ NR, $n=12$ R, Posterior $n=15$ NR, $n=14$ R. (C) neurons and their
911 location in the VMHvl and across the AP axis. Scale bar $200\mu\text{m}$.

912

913 **Table 2 - Morphological profile of PR+ and PR- neurons across the reproductive**
914 **cycle and the AP axis.**

915 Dendrites per neuron: genotype/phase interaction $F(1, 173)=7.85$, $p=0.01$; Branch
916 points per neuron: genotype/phase interaction $F(1, 173)=8.81$, $p=0.02$. L1*- Primary
917 dendrites per neuron: location $F(2, 173)=3.14$, $p=0.04$. L2*- Length of LPDs:
918 genotype/phase interaction $F(1, 168)=6.67$, $p=0.01$, location $F(2, 168)=9.73$, $p<0.0001$.
919 Three-way ANOVA, Sidak correction for multiple comparison. Values expressed as
920 Median (IQR). * $p<0.05$

921 **Figure 7 – The dendritic properties of PR+ neurons are differently modulated**
922 **across the reproductive cycle depending on the location in the AP axis and differ**
923 **from the PR- population.**

924 (A) Schematic representation of the Sholl analysis of a posterior PR+ neuron of a non-
925 receptive female and a posterior PR+ neuron of a receptive female (The axon, visible in
926 this case, depicted in lighter shade and not considered for analysis). (B) Confocal image
927 of the posterior PR+ neuron of a receptive female depicted in A filled with biocytin and
928 stained with streptavidin-Alexa 488 Conjugated. Scale bar 50 μ m. Sholl profiles of (C-E)
929 PR+ Anterior n=19 NR, n=15 R, Medial n=17 NR, n=19 R, Posterior n=20 NR, n=16 R
930 and (F-H) PR- neurons Anterior n=16 NR, n=10 R, Medial n=12 NR, n=12 R, Posterior
931 n=15 NR, n=14 R across the reproductive cycle. (E) The posterior PR+ neurons of
932 receptive females show higher proximal complexity than the ones from non-receptive
933 females (distance from soma x phase of the cycle $F(40, 136)=3.10$, $p<0.0001$, multiple
934 comparison $p<0.001$ at 120 μ m, $p<0.0001$ at 140-160 μ m, $p<0.01$ at 180-200 μ m, and
935 $p=0.04$ at 220 μ m). (G) Medial PR- neurons from receptive females show lower
936 complexity than the ones from non-receptive females (distance from soma x phase of
937 the cycle $F(33, 726)=2.27$, $p<0.0001$, multiple comparison $p=0.03$ in 320-340 μ m). (G)
938 The medial PR+ neurons have lower distal branching than the medial PR- neurons
939 (distance from soma x genotype $F(35, 2030)=2.84$, $p<0.0001$, G^* - multiple comparison
940 $p=0.04$ at 320 μ m, $p<0.01$ at 340-360 μ m $p=0.03$ at 380 μ m) and (H) the posterior PR+
941 neurons have lower proximal branching than the PR- neurons (distance from soma x
942 genotype $F(40, 2520)=1.77$, $p<0.01$). Two-way ANOVA with repeated measures. Mean
943 (\pm SEM).

944 **Figure 8 – The spine density of the LPD of posterior PR+ neurons changes across**
945 **the reproductive cycle.**

946 (A) Spine density of the SPDs Anterior n=15 NR, n=13 R, Medial n=15 NR, n=17 R,
947 Posterior n=15 NR, n=14 R and the (B) LPDs Anterior n=15 NR, n=13 R, Medial n=15
948 NR, n=17 R, Posterior n=13 NR, n=14 R of PR+ neurons across the reproductive cycle.
949 The spine density of the LPDs of posterior PR+ neurons is reduced in receptive females
950 (multiple comparison $p=0.0170$, causing a change in the three-way interaction between
951 the phase of the reproductive cycle, the location in the AP axis and the genotype on the
952 LPDs, $F(2, 150)=4.81$, $p=0.01$). (C) Spine density of the SPDs Anterior n=15 NR, n=10
953 R, Medial n=12 NR, n=17 R, Posterior n=15 NR, n=12 R and the (D) LPDs Anterior
954 n=15 NR, n=10 R, Medial n=12 NR, n=11 R, Posterior n=15 NR, n=12 R of PR- neurons
955 across the reproductive cycle. (E) PR+ neurons have lower spine density on the SPDs
956 (G^{**} - genotype $F(1, 153)=26.21$, $p<0.01$) and also (F) lower spine density on the LPDs
957 (G^* - genotype $F(1, 150)=7.25$, $p=0.01$) than the PR- neurons. Three-way ANOVA,
958 Sidak correction for multiple comparison. Medians (\pm 25-75 percentile). * $p<0.05$.
959 ** $p<0.01$

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1190 **Author contribution**

1191 ICD, NG and SQL designed the research. ICD, NG and LF performed the research. ICD
1192 and NG analyzed the data. ICD, NG and SQL wrote the paper.

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PR+ neurons

	Non-receptive						Receptive					
	Anterior (n=10)		Medial (n=8)		Posterior (n=11)		Anterior (n=9)		Medial (n=11)		Posterior (n=11)	
	T	P	T	P	T	P	T	P	T	P	T	P
Capacitance (pF)	9.03 (2.31)		11.57 (2.66) L1*		7.34 (5.02) L1*		11.45 (3.04)		10.04 (2.256) L1*		9.57 (2.70) L1*	
	9.08	8.99	11.59	7.83	8.21	7.34	11.45	9.87	10.04	9.26	9.57	10.17
Membrane Resistance (MΩ)	970.64 (1012.68)		788.77 (384.09)		912.00 (1209.69)		998.98 (604.43)		823.46 (853.00)		1082.56 (687.92)	
	1017. 11	570.1 9	744.5 4	1231. 50	999.6 5	912.0 0	998.9 8	1326. 90	724.0 9	1116. 09	995.9 3	1082. 56
Time Constant (ms)	0.31 (0.09) L2*		0.36 (0.16)		0.22 (0.08) L2*		0.36 (0.18) L2*		0.27 (0.20)		0.24 (0.16) L2*	
	0.32	0.28	0.36	0.18	0.24	0.20	0.34	0.42	0.26	0.27	0.30	0.23

PR- neurons

	Non-receptive						Receptive					
	Anterior (n=16)		Medial (n=10)		Posterior (n=10)		Anterior (n=11)		Medial (n=11)		Posterior (n=13)	
	T	P	T	P	T	P	T	P	T	P	T	P
Capacitance (pF)	11.04 (4.70)		10.05 (1.89) L1*		8.82 (2.53) L1*		10.54 (2.90)		9.54 (1.28) L1*		10.53 (2.20) L1*	
	11.04	-	10.54	8.69	8.82	8.71	10.54	-	9.53	10.02	10.16	11.60
Membrane Resistance (MΩ)	808.55 (438.933)		1025.83 (425.53)		861.21 (284.09)		1258.25 (1412.35)		884.96 (654.043)		871.47 (556.16)	
	808.5 5	-	1142. 86	781.9 2	873.9 4	861.2 1	1258. 25	-	888.2 0	884.9 6	830.5 5	1160. 18
Time Constant (ms)	0.36 (0.19) L2*		0.34 (0.18)		0.35 (0.17) L2*		0.36 (0.08) L2*		0.30 (0.11)		0.28 (0.16) L2*	
	0.36	-	0.38	0.23	0.34	0.37	0.36	-	0.29	0.34	0.28	0.32

PR+ neurons

	Non-receptive			Receptive		
	Anterior (n=19)	Medial (n=17)	Posterior (n=20)	Anterior (n=15)	Medial (n=19)	Posterior (n=16)
Soma area (μm^2)	184.88 (68.97)	217.01 (95.72)	193.08 (53.31)	219.77 (75.28)	182.92 (38.98)	219.31 (53.94)
Dendrites/neuron	7.00 (2.00)	7.00 (3.00)	6.00 (3.50)	7.00 (3.00)	9.00 (3.00)	7.50 (1.00)
Primary dendrites/neuron	4.00 (1.00)	4.00 (1.00)	3.50 (1.00)	4.00 (1.00)	4.00 (1.00)	3.50 (1.75)
Branch points/neuron	$L1^*$	$L1^*$		$L1^*$	$L1^*$	
Dendritic length of LPDs	3.00 (2.00)	3.00 (3.00)	3.00 (3.00)	4.00 (3.00)	5.00 (4.00)	4.00 (1.75)
Average dendritic length of SPDs	572.69 (199.05)	$L2^*$ 448.43 (268.22)	$L2^*$ 337.53 (287.65)	$L2^*$ 640.69 (277.72)	$L2^*$ 473.32 (273.33)	$L2^*$ 482.57 (202.10)
Average dendritic length of SPDs	205.36 (102.82)	214.50 (65.76)	145.53 (93.24)	181.54 (71.97)	170.55 (77.82)	177.85 (75.57)

PR- neurons

	Non-receptive			Receptive		
	Anterior (n=16)	Medial (n=12)	Posterior (n=15)	Anterior (n=10)	Medial (n=12)	Posterior (n=14)
Soma area (μm^2)	183.64 (58.52)	208.24 (66.82)	171.12 (105.02)	177.00 (124.49)	188.30 (112.71)	184.28 (68.46)
Dendrites/neuron	8.00 (4.00)	7.50 (3.50)	7.00 (3.00)	7.00 (1.50)	7.00 (2.50)	7.00 (2.75)
Primary dendrites/neuron	4.00 (1.75)	3.00 (1.00)	4.00 (2.00)	3.50 (2.25)	3.00 (0.75)	4.00 (1.25)
Branch points/neuron	$L1^*$	$L1^*$		$L1^*$	$L1^*$	
Dendritic length of LPDs	4.00 (5.50)	4.00 (3.50)	3.00 (2.00)	3.00 (3.25)	4.00 (1.00)	3.00 (3.25)
Average dendritic length of SPDs	642.64 (235.57)	$L2^*$ 644.05 (96.20)	$L2^*$ 509.16 (253.81)	$L2^*$ 566.10 (352.88)	$L2^*$ 494.52 (289.21)	$L2^*$ 389.96 (194.99)
Average dendritic length of SPDs	155.87 (62.25)	255.72 (102.05)	172.95 (79.60)	124.89 (60.77)	150.58 (134.84)	176.90 (85.55)